

Enhancing the Nurse-Patient Communication and Patient Satisfaction

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Background

- Effective nurse-patient communication:
 - is key to improving patient satisfaction with care
 - includes active listening, being present, timely sharing of pertinent information and understanding the patient perspective
 - has been shown to decrease patient anxiety, shorten hospital length of stay and increase patient sense of control and confidence regarding their health care
- Commit to Sit is a communication strategy that has been shown to improve patient satisfaction

Problem

- In 2021, our organization implemented The HOPE Experience: A Model of Human Compassion to improve patient satisfaction; however, in 2023 Consumer Assessment of Healthcare Providers & Systems (CAHPS) scores for nursing communication fell below the hospital's expected 90th percentile ranking

Purpose

To enhance The HOPE Experience Program by incorporating the "Commit to Sit" component and assessing its impact on improving patient satisfaction

Aims: a) Increase nurses' knowledge and skills on implementing the elements of the "Commit to Sit" strategy; b) Document the number of nurses who implemented the new "Commit to Sit" strategy; and c) Evaluate patient satisfaction as measured by the CAHPS Top Box Scores for nursing communication

Frameworks

Iowa Model Revised: Evidenced-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

The HOPE Experience Program Framework

Core Principles H-O-P-E	The HOPE Experience Core Practices to guide interactions with patients and caregivers
Connect with Heart by...	Acknowledging, making eye contact, and introducing their role, and calls patient by their name
Offer service with collaboration and a sense of urgency by...	Explaining their actions, asking if they have questions, responding to questions, and taking ownership of concerns until resolved
Personalize by...	Listening, validating, empathizing, clarifying, respecting cultural uniqueness, and explaining next steps for processes/procedures, and updates the communication board
End with excellence by...	Sharing contact information, updates communication board, asks if there is anything else they can do before leaving the room, and says thank you before exiting room

Results

Pre-Post Knowledge Survey Results

The HOPE Experience Program Pre/Post Categories Composite Score (Paired Observations N=32)	P value	Statistically Significant
H – Connect with Heart	p = .768	No
O – Offer service with a sense of urgency	p = .009	Yes
P – Personalize	p = .229	No
E – End with excellence	p = .021	Yes
Pre/Post ALL HOPE Categories Composite Scores	p = .001	Yes

Methods

Design: Pre and post-test design
Sample: 40 RNs received the educational intervention between Sep – Oct 2023
Setting: 33-bed medical oncology inpatient unit with 6 double-bed occupancy rooms, NCI-designated Comprehensive Cancer Center with Magnet designation located in Southern CA
Data Collection/Measures:

- Pre/Post knowledge level measured using a survey (subjective) administered pre and post educational intervention
- Practice change measured via observations (objective) audits
- Patient satisfaction measured using the CAHPS Top Box Scores for nursing communication

Limitations

- Identified barriers to sitting during patient interactions due to insufficient chairs in rooms, especially double-bed rooms, and inconsistent patient room sizes
- Small sample size for post-survey questionnaire limited ability to generalize results

Conclusion

- The "Commit to Sit" communication strategy observations showed statistically significant practice change; however, the CAPHS scores for nursing communication were not significantly improved

Sustainability

- The HOPE Experience program is supported by this organization
- Continue to provide staff education on the "Commit to Sit" communication strategy and perform ongoing random observation audits of The HOPE Experience and "Commit to Sit" to inform practice change

References

